

A CROSS-SECTIONAL ASSESSMENT OF PARENTS' SATISFACTION TOWARD PAEDIATRIC PHYSICAL THERAPY IN PESHAWAR

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Abstract

BACKGROUND: This study attempts to find out how satisfied parents are with their children's physical therapy treatments. Children with varied physical limitations or impairments benefit greatly from physical therapy in terms of their general health and functioning capacities. The study includes a thorough survey of parents of kids who had received physical therapy in a variety of healthcare facilities. The effectiveness of the therapy, interactions with medical personnel, perceived improvements in the child's condition, and general happiness with the therapy were all included in the survey.

OBJECTIVE: To determine the level of parent satisfaction regarding physical therapy treatment among pediatric population in Peshawar.

METHODOLOGY: A cross-sectional study conducted in Peshawar, comprising of 190 participants. Data was collected from Akbar Kare Institute, Town Women and Children Hospital and Habib physiotherapy complex. Non probability convenient sampling technique was used; data was collected through WHO curriculum for parent's satisfaction questionnaire and was analysed through SPSS version 26.

RESULT: A total of 190 parents of Akbar kare institute, Town women and children hospital, Habib physiotherapy complex were recruited. Out of 190 participants, mean age of parents was 32.88 years. Demographic data showed that 67 (35.3%) respondents were males, while 123(64.7%) were females. Maximum age group responded were 77 (38.6%) range from 30-39 years and minimum were 14 (7.3%) ranged 50-59 years. About 110(57.9%) parents are strongly agree that I was satisfied with overall quality of my physical therapy care and 72(37.9%) are agree and 2(1.1%) are disagree and 6(3.2%) are neither agree nor disagree.

CONCLUSION: In conclusion, this study explored the satisfaction levels of

parents in Peshawar regarding physical therapy treatment in pediatrics settings. The findings revealed that a majority of parents expressed high levels of satisfaction with the therapy their children received. This indicates that physical therapy plays a vital role in improving the well-being and functional abilities of children with physical disabilities or impairments

INTRODUCTION

Pediatric Physical Therapy: Pediatric Physical therapy provides care for a wide range of kids with different conditions and needs. According to parent satisfaction surveys, treatment greatly benefits from the therapist-patient interaction.[1]. As the child's primary caregiver, the family is essential to safeguarding their health and well-being. In Bly's view, therapeutic management becomes more consistent when family members are involved. For this reason, healthcare professionals should involve family members in all aspects of planning, delivering, and evaluating health and developmental services when working with small children. [2]. Parents are in a unique position to assess their child's requirements, and this competence extends to the demands of therapy. Parent satisfaction research has looked at the therapeutic alliance and the dynamics between parents, kids, and therapists. [2]. The World Health Organization's (WHO) International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health (ICF) defines developmental, neuromuscular, cardiorespiratory, and musculoskeletal conditions. The American Physical Therapy Association (APTA) Academy of Pediatric Physical Therapy (APPT) supports the development of clinical practice guidelines (CPG) to aid pediatric physical therapists (PTs) in the identification and management of infants and children with participation restrictions, activity limitations, and body function and structure[3].

In assessing the quality and effectiveness of a particular healthcare service, patient satisfaction is considered to be a critical component. Research has shown that patients with higher satisfaction ratings also exhibit better health [4]. There are 13.9 million disabled people in the United Kingdom. 1.1 million, or nearly 8%, of this category are children and young people. This showed that one child out of every twenty had a disability.[5]. Physical therapy has a number of characteristics that could affect how

satisfied a patient is: it usually requires the patient to actively participate in the process, takes longer than a standard medical visit, involves more physical contact, and may be painful or perceived as physically threatening. [6].

As has been shown for patient satisfaction in medical care, the most constant factor influencing patient satisfaction across all trials in our study was the therapist's qualities 12, 13, 20, 23, 24, and so on. 42 High levels of satisfaction are specifically correlated with a physical therapist's expertise, education, professionalism, kind demeanor, and efficient communication. Patients value communication skills such as being able to describe their disease in a way that is understandable, providing information about their prognosis, and outlining their role in the treatment process.[7]. A systematic pediatric physical therapy program was found to be more effective than standard treatment in preventing or minimizing skull deformation in babies with positional preference at 6 months of age.[8]. This study illuminates parent's typically good experience with Peshawar physical therapy services. It emphasizes the significance of continuing to provide high -quality treatment and politely interacting with medical staff. However, the cost and availability of these services continue to be major issues, highlighting the necessity for additional study and legislative actions to increase the financial accessibility and inclusivity of physical therapy for all persons and families.

The main outcome of pediatric care is the child's health improving or their symptoms becoming better. However, parents' satisfaction with care can be utilized as a useful proxy variable for various important aspects of care quality because it is linked to so many vital outcomes, including understanding medical information and adhering to the treatment regimen[9]. There are two main reasons why parents should be involved in their child's medical care. The first argument focuses on child functioning. To

transmit physical treatment from the rehabilitation center to the child's everyday functioning, therapeutic exercises must be incorporated into habitual practice. Parental involvement may be crucial in this transfer. The second factor is how it will affect the parent's status. [10]. The family and the therapists must work together to create individualized rehabilitation strategies that effectively support the child's functionality. Parents are concerned about how the lessons learned in the therapeutic environment will be implemented at home and in school, and they are interested in learning strategies that will help their kid perform better in functional activities of daily living. [11]. There is evidence that satisfaction influences improvements in health status and aids in the assessment of communication styles, making it a critical success indicator. The latter is particularly important in pediatric care because the children and their accompanying patients must be satisfied with the standard of care. [12][13].

Parent satisfaction in health care refers to how well the services provided to their children meet the needs, expectations, and desires of the parents. Given their significant impact on their offspring's growth, parents' viewpoints and contentment are critical to improving health care [14]. The treatment strategy outlined places more emphasis on strengthening programs and positioning the home for parents than it does on hands-on passive range of motion [15]. In the field of physiotherapy, the therapeutic alliance is more robust than in other medical specializations. Consequently, there may be a direct impact on the patient's perception of this relationship. This mainly has to do with how physical therapy is administered and how much the patient and therapist interact. [4].

Most people seeking rehabilitation treatments are either patients or parents of disabled children hoping to minimize the effects of their child's disability. Among those therapies is physiotherapy. [16]. Paediatric physical therapy aims to improve function in newborns and early childhood learners. Physical therapy is often provided by a pediatric physical therapist. [17]. professional as If a disease or accident stunts a child's growth, it may keep them from developing as freely as other kids. Because of the

differences in their rehabilitation requirements from adult rehabilitation, they might need to see a paediatric expert. With the help of a pediatric physical therapy they develop alongside their classmates, they can benefit from the maximum mobility and function as well as fewer hurdles to typical mobility. [18]. A paediatric physical therapist who works with your family can help your kid improve their abilities, function, and movement. As many restrictions as possible can be removed in order to help your child achieve the maximum amount of functional mobility. [19]. Nurses, pediatric physiotherapists, and pediatricians working in the Neonatal Intensive Care Unit should be aware of the requirements and options of parents in order to address those needs. [18]. Most children receiving paediatric critical care may not be able to express their needs and emotions. In this instance, it is accepted that parents' experiences define excellence at the outset. The family-centered care approaches presented in this viewpoint require parental involvement in daily care. [20]. One important indicator of how well the child is being cared for is how happy the parents are with the medical care they have gotten. Happiness is the goal of health care delivery, not only a means of measuring quality. Enticing parents to actively participate in the care of their young child and spend more time with them increases their level of satisfaction. [21].

LITERATURE REVIEW

Role Of Parents As Co-Therapist: A study of Lucretia et al. Adri Vermeer developmental medicine and child neurology 45, 58-69, in 2003. [22][10] a major change regarding parental involvement began in the early 1980s. Prior to this, parents were frequently excluded from their children's counseling. Physical therapists recently became more conscious of potential parental roles. Parents today play an active, participative role rather than a passive one. As a result, parents act as a form of co-therapist with the therapist, who chose the treatment strategies, while the parents carry out treatment activities at home under the therapist's supervision. [21]

Parents Satisfaction Level Regarding CP Children: A study was done by Mian Ali Raza, Umer Maqsood, Faiza Sharif, Hafiz Sheraz Arshad University of

Lahore in 2018.)[22] This study examines parents' perceptions of physical therapy for kids with diplegic cerebral palsy. It is a posture and movement disorder. It affects roughly 2.6 out of every 1000 children and is a well-known cause of impairment in kids all over the world. Physical therapists are excellent examples of this. Pediatric rehabilitation services play an important role to increase the level of satisfaction among parents regarding these services. In this study they compare both government and private hospitals. They included 100 patients from government hospitals, 69 were males and 31 were females, whereas in private hospitals, out of 100 patients, 44 were males and 56 were females. Compared to government facilities, parents of children with cerebral palsy in private hospitals expressed greater satisfaction. (22)

Rehman Abdelhamid Mohmand et al. conducted a study that was published in *The Egyptian Journal of Hospital Medicine* 89, 5386-5391, in 2022.[4] One hundred parents of children between the ages of two and seven who had spastic cerebral palsy participated in this study. The Med Risk instrument (MRPS) was used to gauge parent satisfaction, and the pediatric quality of life scale (PedsQI) was used to gauge children's health-related quality of life. The outcomes showed that the parents were happy. (23) A study of Marie O Mir, Cliona O'Sullivan, Catherine Blake, Olive Lennon, *pediatric physical therapy* 31, 192-199, in 2019.[23] High levels of parent satisfaction with a unique advanced practice in pediatric orthopedics were found in this study, which also highlighted both positive and negative perspectives that affect parents' perceptions of the quality of care. They employed an open-ended questionnaire with visit specific satisfaction (VSQ) questions. The mean (95% CI) of the responses was then calculated. Parental satisfaction scores were great overall.

Significance of How Parents See Physical Therapy Services: a study of Snaefridur Thora Eglison et al. published in *Journal of Caring Sciences* in 2011.[24] In this study, it was explored how parents see physical therapy services for their physically challenged kids. They conducted open interviews with 17 parents of children aged 7 to 13 (14 mothers and 3 fathers), who were chosen through a deliberate selection. They were categorized into nine groups

and arranged under three major themes. Numerous compliments were offered, however many parents received inadequate information about the objectives of the intervention. The majority of parents expressed a desire for cooperation and respect while planning interventions. This study thus emphasizes the significance of respecting the needs and desires of both parents and children. In this sense, parents' ought to actively participate in helping their kids choose priorities and develop implementation plans. Parents also requested that the therapists give greater care to the child's circumstances and environment.

Another study of Anne JA Kruijsen-Terpstra, et al. Examining the needs and experiences of parents of young children with cerebral palsy, ages 2-4, undergoing physical therapy in rehabilitation setting was the aim of this study. Among them were twenty-one parents of young children with cerebral palsy. They spoke with those parents in qualitative interviews. The results showed that the three primary themes in parents' experiences with their child's therapy were partnership, communication, and knowledge. As a result, a large number of the study's themes seem to be essential to understanding the needs and experiences.

The study's aim was to investigate how parents experience objectives and goal setting. Based on interviews with 39 parents of cerebral palsy children who lived in western Canada, they conducted a qualitative study. They looked at five topics that reflected the parents' objectives for occupational and physical therapy goal-setting. Their objectives were to move, stay physically active, live happy, fulfilled lives that were accepted by others, receive balancing therapy, and fulfil duties and obligations. Consequently, the parents' intended degree of involvement in goal-setting as well as the goals that held meaning for them shifted. This illustrated the importance of cultivating a genuine and reliable relationship with the families in order to have candid conversations about family objectives, values, and unique situations.[26]

Satisfaction level of parents with paediatric rehabilitation services: In 2001, Gillian King, Tamzin Cathers, Susanne King, and Peter Rosenbaum conducted a study in *Children's Health Care* 30(2).13] The service elements that affect

parents' contentment with the pediatric rehabilitation services their kids received are included in this study. 130 of the 645 parents in the study were judged to be extremely satisfied, while 101 parents were determined to be rather unsatisfied based on their score on a standardized satisfaction scale. The three services that parents loved the most and the least were as follows. Parents who were extremely satisfied with their child's care also emphasized receiving supportive and courteous attention (i.e., feeling heard and having service providers' reports taken seriously). The waiting list must be cut down, parents must be treated with respect, and supportive care must be provided

METHODOLOGY

Study Design: This study was conducted through a descriptive cross-sectional framework on 190 participants were parents of children, 1-16 years of age, who currently were receiving or had received pediatric physical therapy in an outpatient setting. Participation was voluntary by all parents.

Settings of the study: The data was collected in the three pediatric physical therapy institutes of Peshawar namely; Habib Physiotherapy Institute, Akbar Kare Institute, Town Women and Children's Hospital, Pak Medical Centre.

Study Population: The study population consisted of both male and female parents of children 1-16 years of age who were taking treatments from Habib Physiotherapy Complex, Akbar Kare Institute, and Town Women and Children Hospital

Sampling Technique: Non-Probability Convenient Sampling

Sample Size: The sample size was calculated, using Rao Soft software and the sample size for population of 372 in the said institutes was 190.

Eligibility

Age of participants

Age groups	Frequency	Percent
20 to 29 years	72	34.2

Inclusion Criteria: Parents (Both father or mother) of children having age 1-16 years. Parents of physically disable or handicap children, the follow-up of more than 3 months patients were included.

Exclusion criteria: Those parents whose were unwilling to give the data were excluded. Data from Guardian were also exclusion criteria, children of Physiotherapist were also excluded to avoid biasness.

Ethical Consideration: A written informed consent was obtained from each of the participants. Relevant information about the study was provided both verbally and in a written form to the participants. The personal information of the participants was guaranteed and it was assured to them that their personal information will not be mentioned anywhere in the report.

Data collection tool: Physical therapy patient satisfaction questionnaire was used for data collection. The higher the score on the parental satisfaction questionnaire, which has a maximum value of 5, the more satisfied the user is with the service. On a scale of 1 to 5, the majority of the acquired. According to the current results, statement 26—"If I had to, I would pay for these physical therapy services myself"—had the lowest score on the parental satisfaction questionnaire, while question 27—"Overall, I was satisfied with my experience with physical therapy"—had the highest score.

Analysis Technique: The Statistical Package for Social Science [SPSS version 26] was used for data analysis

RESULTS

Demographic Information: Out of 190 participants, mean age of parents was 32.88 years. Demographic data showed that 67 (35.3%) respondents were males, while 123 (64.7%) were females. Maximum age group responded were 77 (38.6%) range from 30-39 years and minimum were 14 (7.3%) ranged 50-59 years.

30 to 39 years	77	38.6
40 to 49 years	27	4.1
50 to 59 years	14	7.3
Total	190	100

About 114 parents (or 60%) highly agree that the physical therapist was polite to them, 73 parents (or 38.4%) agree, 1 parent (or.5%) disagrees, and 1 parent (or.5%) definitely disagrees. About 100 parents (52.6%) strongly agree that they were happy

with the physical therapist's therapy, 86 parents (45.3%) agree, and 4 parents (2.1%) are unsure. About 106 parents, 55.8%, strongly agree that they were happy with the service provided by Physical Therapist.

Parents are divided on whether their physical therapist understood their child's or their own problems: 117 (61.6%) highly agree, 67 (35.3%) agree, 1 (.5%) disagree, and 4 (2.1%) are neither in agreement nor disagreement.

The directions I received from my physical therapist were useful, according to about 118 parents (62.1%),

64 parents (33.7%), 1 parent (.5%), 3 parents (1.6%), and 7 parents (3.7%) who are unsure. About 110 parents, 57.9%, strongly agree that I was satisfied with the overall quality of my physical therapy care; 72 parents, 37.9%, agree; 2 parents, 1.1%, disagree; and 6 parents, or 3.2%, were unsure.

I was satisfied with overall quality of my physical therapy care.

Of the parents surveyed, 107 (56.3%) highly agree that they would suggest this facility to friends or family, 78 (41.1%) agree, 1 (.5%) strongly disagree, and 4 (2.1%) were unsure. 108 parents, or 56.8%, firmly agree that if I ever needed physical therapy services again, I would come back to this facility. Furthermore, 77 (40.5%) of respondents agree, 1

(.5%) disagree, 1 (0.5%) severely disagree, and 3 (1.6%) are neither in agreement nor disagreement. 125 parents, or 65.8%, strongly agree that, overall, they were satisfied with their experience with physical therapy; 59 parents, or 31.1%, agree, 1 parent, or .5%, disagree, and 5 parents, or 2.6%, are unsure.

Overall, I was satisfied with my experience with physical therapy.

DISCUSSION:

The Bluestein C study found a negative correlation between waiting time and patient satisfaction

levels.[27] In a similar vein, Krietz et al. found that patient satisfaction declines with longer wait times..[28] The time spent with the doctor was a

stronger predictor of patient satisfaction than waiting time, despite the fact that Anderson et al. also demonstrated that longer waiting times had a detrimental impact on patient satisfaction. They were content with the appropriate consultation; waiting time was the next best indicator of patient satisfaction, after the patient's faith in the physician..[29]In our study, 107 out of 190 parents strongly agreed that they were seen promptly when they arrived for treatment because, in our country, parents don't have to wait around for too long because doctors are easily accessible and available five days a week. In other countries, such as the UK and the USA, parents must wait around for too long and cannot easily access. While earlier research indicated that participants in the CIMT program successfully completed the program—despite some parents reporting that participation was challenging—all parents reported satisfaction with the program at the conclusion of the 3-week intervention, supporting our current study's findings that 95.50 percent of parents are satisfied with physical therapy.[30] In line with our findings, 95.50% of parents in Malaysia expressed pleasure with physical therapy, and survey results there also showed that parents and caregivers there had an overall satisfaction level of 98.1 % with the community-based treatments their impaired children got [31].

Nonclinical factors also have an impact on patient satisfaction. Our results indicate that the following items had low scores (below 4 on a 1 to 5): statement 20 “The parking was available for me,” and question 16 “The location of the facility was convenient for me.” This is consistent with the findings of Hills and Kitchen (25), who stated that numerous studies have found that patients are more satisfied if the physiotherapy service is easy to access (location, parking, and clinic hours), involves helpful administrative staff, and is linked to shorter waiting times..[32]

And in our study about 35.3% parents are strongly agree that the location was convenient for me and rest of the parents told that the location was too far away from them because these parents come from other cities the other reason was that the physical therapy facilities is not available in their near city and they come here for their child rehabilitation for that reason they are little satisfied due to location

problem. According to similar results from the patient satisfaction survey, a high percentage of families with children with cystic fibrosis were satisfied with the community's specialized physiotherapy support [33]. The majority of parents and caregivers in this study expressed satisfaction with the physiotherapist's explanation of their activities while working with the kid, according to an analysis of their reports. While a majority of them expressed satisfaction with the practical solutions and/or alternatives their physiotherapist offered, particularly with regard to home programs and the required appliances, a smaller percentage expressed satisfaction with the physiotherapist's competence. Furthermore, the few parents and caregivers who had worked with a physiotherapist who helped them solve. The parents and caregivers in this group were also pleased with the service they received. Nonetheless, the majority of parents and caregivers believed that the instruction was insufficient, which left them unhappy.[34]

CONCLUSION: In conclusion, this study, which involved 190 parents at several medical facilities in Peshawar, according to the study, several parents had previously undergone physical therapy, and most of them reported having favorable interactions with their physical therapists. The majority of parents indicated highly satisfaction with the care and assistance they received, suggesting that the physical therapists were kind, perceptive of their issues, and helpful in giving advice.

LIMITATIONS The study was conducted with a specific sample of parents from various medical facilities in Peshawar. The findings may not be representative the broader population, as they are limited to this specific group. Parents who couldn't pay cost or any transport issues.

RECOMMENDATIONS: Future studies should include a broader range of paediatric conditions such as muscular dystrophy, torticollis, and general developmental disorders, beyond just physical disabilities, to better understand parental satisfaction. Additional influencing factors like socioeconomic status, cultural background, and healthcare facility conditions should also be explored. Clear and

transparent communication between parents, therapists, and healthcare providers is essential, encouraging active parental involvement in treatment planning. Lastly, recognizing the emotional impact of paediatric therapy on parents, healthcare teams should offer psychological support and resources to help families manage stress and anxiety effectively.

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